

Mental health challenges among older adults

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Dear Readers,

The world's population is aging at a growing rate. From 2015 to 2050, the number of people aged 60 and up is expected to double, going from about 900 million to 2 billion adults over 60. One in four older adults experiences issues with their mental health, contributing to 23% of the total global burden of disease associated with diseases related to older adults. Life events related to aging, such as bereavement, loneliness, social isolation, and decreased finances after retirement, can add to the psychological burden of older adults [1]. Loneliness and social isolation, in particular, are associated with adverse mental health outcomes, including dementia, depression, and generalized anxiety disorder. The decline in physical and psychological health of older adults can reciprocally worsen social stressors, leading to further stress, difficulties in accessing care, and subsequent deterioration of health [2].

Considering that 15% of these individuals struggle with some form of mental health disorder and that neurological and mental issues account for more than 6% of disability in this age group, we are facing a potential crisis. The data regarding the prevalence and structure of mental disorders in old people significantly vary [3]. The most common conditions include anxiety, severe cognitive impairment, and mood disorders such as depression or bipolar disorder. Depression and dementia are the most prevalent, affecting 5% to 7% of the population over 60, followed closely by anxiety, which affects 3.8% of older adults, according to the World Health Organization (WHO). Mental health problems can significantly impact an older person's ability to carry out basic daily living activities, reducing their independence, autonomy, and quality of life. The first step to mitigate these negative consequences is to make a diagnosis. Unfortunately, mental health problems are often undiagnosed and untreated, leaving many older people without proper help [4].

Today's older adult population is not likely to acknowledge mental illness or access mental health services due to stigma. Many view mental illness as a sign of weakness and are unlikely to admit to experiencing problems, especially when they fear loss of independence. Symptoms of dementia and depression are often considered a normal part of aging, and many older people also lack the availability of and access to services [5].

Challenges also arise from the workforce: few mental health providers have specialized training in providing care for older adults, and many harbor societal-transmitted biases themselves. This therapeutic pessimism among health professionals leads to a belief that it is too late for psychiatric care to be effective for older people. As a result, there is a lack of investment in the development of policies, strategies, programs, and services for older persons with mental health problems. Given the rapid growth of the older population, it will be challenging for countries, regardless of income levels, to develop a specific workforce to treat and care for older people with mental health disorders at the same rate. Therefore, utilizing other existing resources becomes mandatory; primary care must be leveraged [6]. To address these issues, it is essential to incorporate geriatrics education and training for health care professionals, encourage community participation

and social interaction, and develop specialized mental health services for older adults. By doing so, we can improve the mental health care system for older adults and reduce the impact of mental health problems on their quality of life [7,8]. In conclusion, prioritizing the mental health of older adults is not merely a compassionate act; it is a vital one that significantly enhances their quality of life and fosters healthy and successful aging. By acknowledging and addressing the mental health challenges faced by older adults, we can empower them to maintain their independence, engage more fully in their communities, and experience the richness of life in their later years. Mental well-being is a cornerstone of holistic health, and as such, it should be given the same attention and care as physical health. When we invest in the mental health of older adults, we contribute to a society that values and supports its members at every stage of life, ensuring that our golden years are lived with dignity, joy, and fulfillment.

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